

Research Plan: The Hacker's Mind

Anonymous

1 Introduction and Context

Offensive computer security, colloquially also known as “hacking”, has turned from fun into profit. Due to the severe lack of talent, the monetary compensation for offensive security professionals is often among the highest for IT professionals. Due to this combination, interest into automation of hacking tasks is high, sparking academic and commercial research.

One of the authors, is one of those hackers: after spending ten years primarily testing web-applications he embarked on a PhD-Journey focusing upon the application of machine learning on security. Following academic tradition, the first stage of the journey was the creation of a survey paper during which a mismatch was found: the pen-testing areas that the papers chose to optimize were orthogonal to tasks that pen-testers realistically perform.

This is the motivation for this paper: to find out how hackers work and think. Audiences are both researchers wanting to improve the status quo as well as practitioners that want to reflect upon their practice.

To clarify some terms: Security Professional (SP) includes both offensive and defensive professions. The “professional” term for offensive security professionals is penetration tester, in short, pen tester. Hacker is often used synonymously with Pen-Tester but denotes a person who subverts the technology to achieve goals that were not intended by the original authors. We use the term hacker for brevity from now on.

The primary interviewer is suited for this research as he is already embedded into the local hacking community, national standardization institutions as well as international non-profit organizations such as OWASP.

We hope that this research proposal meets the rigor criteria as defined by Meyer et al. [9].

1.1 Related Work

To the best of our knowledge, there has been no prior work investigating hacker decision-making processes. The existing literature [12] can be roughly divided into two areas: On a high level, standards such as the “Pen-Test Execution Standard” (PTES) describe how a penetration test should be performed on a high-level. They describe subsequent phases that a penetration tester should go through, but do not detail the pen-tester’s decision-making process.

On a low-level, more hands-on hacking primers contain lists of different attacks, categorized by attack vector. They do neither describe how a hacker selects a suiting attack vector nor how they chose attacks out of the selected attack vectors.

Similar conceptual studies have been conducted for the software engineering domain, e.g., in „The design of bug fixes” the decision making process behind selecting bug fixes was the focus of an empirical study [10].

1.2 Ethical and Legal Issues

Our research includes interactions with human beings (chapter 4) thus the research proposal will be submitted to the *Ethics Committee of our Institution* for approval.

We have taken preventive steps during the research design to reduce ethical and legal issues: All interviewees are pseudonymized, and their interviews are partially anonymized (Chapter 6). The selection of data collection methods, as well as interviewees, was filtered due to their ethical impact (Chapters 4 and ??).

2 Overall Methodological Approach

Our initial survey indicated that current research on machine learning (ML) usage for security is predominantly quantitative, e.g., there was an a-priori theory about which areas would benefit from usage of ML; the research itself consists of implementing ML techniques and measuring improvements through metrics. We hypothesize that the target of current research is not guided by the actual needs of hackers and propose to investigate the rich inner workings of human hackers to help selection of research topics that matter to them. This puts our research in qualitative territory.

We have chosen a **pragmatist** approach [8, 11] and will employ **mixed-methods**. Primarily we will employ methods from the *empiricist* or *summarist interpretist* school, such as interviews and surveys. Other aspects of

our research, such as the verification of our findings through analysis of existing artifacts or the discovery of a mental model, are more situated in a *post-positivist* [5] area thus warranting the overall *pragmatic* approach.

3 Research Questions and Expected Contributions

We selected the following research questions for this research proposal:

RQ1: How do hackers “think”? This includes the overall security professional’s approach to performing a pen-test: How do they choose and prioritize their targets? How do they choose their attack classes and vectors? When do they know when to quit?

The expected contribution is a more thorough understanding of a hacker’s mindset; we assume that a mental model, akin to a simplified flow model, can be derived.

RQ2: What are the tedious and / or time-consuming areas of their work? What areas could be improved by better tooling? Which areas are esteemed to be too important to delegate to tools.

The expected contribution is the identification of areas where hackers find tooling to be missing or lacking, e.g., research opportunities that are grounded in the experiences of hackers and matter to them.

4 Research Methods

During our research, we will apply the following research methods [11]:

Semi-Structured Interviews. We assume that most data-gathering will be performed through interviews. We have chosen *exploratory semi-structured interviews* to get a better feel for the landscape. To allow rich contextual data capture, the interviews will be conducted in person.

In addition, we evaluated additional methods, but have chosen not to pursue them during this research project:

Participant Observation. [7] One of the authors is already embedded in the local professional and informal hacking culture. This would allow for rich participatory observations.

This research method was dropped due to ethical and legal considerations: any involvement with white- or black-hat hacking would imply access to potential sensitive data; damages could occur through participation. This prevents us from observing behavior directly; we assume that through the author’s experience and rapport with interviewees, interviews will transport a realistic view of hacking activities.

Autoethnography. [3] Initially we wanted to include our experience as an autoethnography but did not pursue this further as this would have biased the resulting model into a web-application vulnerability-assessment direction. We believe that choosing offensive professionals from multiple distinct areas will lead us to discover a more generic and inclusive mental model. In addition, the chosen analysis technique allows us to include the subjective experience of the authors in a structured way.

5 Interviews

We will conduct semi-structured interviews until theoretical saturation is reached. We will use Thematic Analysis to discover common themes between those interviews. We assume an overall interview count of 12 interviews which falls well within the established saturation limits of 6–12 interviews [6, 4].

All interviews will be performed on neutral territory (pub/coffee houses). With the consent of the interviewee, audio recordings will be made using the native Android audio recorder application. Compensation in the form of 20€ will be offered to participants.

As the interviews will be carried out in person, interviewees will be recruited from the professional hacking scene. Each interviewee will be a security professional in good standing (defined as multiple years of experience or by winning national tournaments). Choosing white-heads will also prevent ethical issues. To gain a broad exposure, interviewees will be distributed over multiple hacking sub-areas, i.e., *web-penetration testing*, *red-teaming*, *exploit-development* and *bug-bounty hunting*.

The objective of the interview is to capture how the interviewees perform and structure their security assignments. To achieve this, the interviews will employ open-ended questions and only a checklist with “topics to be covered” will be prepared. The interviews are scheduled to last at least 60 minutes.

Initial contact with suitable hackers has already been made, with the informal acceptance for interviews given by six. Interviews can start after the *interview question guide* has been finished, we assume that we will be able to schedule two interviews per week, thus allowing four weeks for all interviews to take place.

These initial interviews will be the basis for *Thematic Analysis* (Chapter 7.1).

5.1 Threats to Validity

To allow rich face-to-face conversations, local hackers were selected as interview partners, which could lead to selection bias (*internal threat*).

The author has been performing web application penetration tests for ten years and thus brings his own experience to the table. This might lead to a *experimenter bias* (*internal threat*). Special consideration will be taken to prevent that his experience will lead to biased or leading interview questions.

Hacking contains multiple disciplines. Our derived mental model might only capture common themes of a subset of those (*external validity*). We try to counteract this by inviting interviewees from diverse hacking fields.

6 Data Preparation and Storage

We see three distinct sources of data collection:

Interview data will consist of audio captures and notes written down during the interviews. The identity of the interviewee will be pseudonymized in all written or transcribed documents. We assume that we only have to transcribe key quotes, mentioned targets will be anonymized. Transcription will be performed by hand by the authors thus reducing exposure of data. Conversation notes will be digitalized and the originals destroyed. Data will be stored according to the Institution's and GDPR guidance documents.

7 Data Analysis

We considered different qualitative analysis methods [2] for our collected data and selected *Thematic Analysis* as its focus on detecting themes in the collected data is a good fit for our research objective. We considered *Grounded Theory* but decided against it, as it implies that the researcher does not have a prior theory. In addition, Grounded Theory would warrant a larger sample size than the potential qualified penetration testers available at the local environment. We considered *Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis* but finally decided against it as we focus upon themes across interviews not on the personal experience of a single interviewee. In addition, our potential sample size is larger than sample sizes typically associated with Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis.

7.1 Thematic Analysis

We have chosen *Thematic Analysis* [1] (TA) for the analysis of all interviews, some artifact data, and free-form responses to the survey sent. To summarize, when performing TA the researchers initially familiarize themselves with the data, and extracts of the data are given codes. These codes are then used to create clusters which identify or construct underlying themes. Then, those themes are reviewed, defined, and named. We will perform a **Reflexive Thematic Analysis** in a *inductive* (data-driven, exploratory) manner. To fulfill the quality requirements given by Braun et al. [1] we will reflect, identify and state our assumptions at the beginning of the analysis.

To remain accountable for the data, we will link each code to the audio recordings (including timestamp) or to the meeting notes. To create themes out of codes, mind maps will be utilized. The concrete tooling is not yet defined; we will try to use specialized Qualitative Analysis Software¹ but assume that we will fall back to pen&paper and whiteboards during the investigation.

References

- [1] Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke. Reflecting on reflexive thematic analysis. *Qualitative research in sport, exercise and health*, 11(4):589–597, 2019.
- [2] Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke. Can i use ta? should i use ta? should i not use ta? comparing reflexive thematic analysis and other pattern-based qualitative analytic approaches. *Counselling and Psychotherapy Research*, 21(1):37–47, 2021.
- [3] Carolyn Ellis, Tony E Adams, and Arthur P Bochner. Autoethnography: an overview. *Historical social research/Historische sozialforschung*, pages 273–290, 2011.
- [4] Jill J Francis, Marie Johnston, Clare Robertson, Liz Glidewell, Vikki Entwistle, Martin P Eccles, and Jeremy M Grimshaw. What is an adequate sample size? operationalising data saturation for theory-based interview studies. *Psychology and health*, 25(10):1229–1245, 2010.

¹ Dedoose, <https://www.dedoose.com/>

-
- [5] Egon G Guba, Yvonna S Lincoln, et al. Competing paradigms in qualitative research. *Handbook of qualitative research*, 2(163-194):105, 1994.
- [6] Greg Guest, Arwen Bunce, and Laura Johnson. How many interviews are enough? an experiment with data saturation and variability. *Field methods*, 18(1):59–82, 2006.
- [7] Greg Guest, Emily E Namey, and Marilyn L Mitchell. Participant observation. *Collecting qualitative data: A field manual for applied research*, pages 75–112, 2013.
- [8] Noella Mackenzie and Sally Knipe. Research dilemmas: Paradigms, methods and methodology. *Issues in educational research*, 16(2):193–205, 2006.
- [9] Miriah Meyer and Jason Dykes. Criteria for rigor in visualization design study. *IEEE transactions on visualization and computer graphics*, 26(1):87–97, 2019.
- [10] Emerson Murphy-Hill, Thomas Zimmermann, Christian Bird, and Nachiappan Nagappan. The design of bug fixes. In *2013 35th International Conference on Software Engineering (ICSE)*, pages 332–341, 2013.
- [11] MNK Saunders and PC Tosey. The layers of research design. Technical report, University of Surrey, 2013.
- [12] Aleatha Shanley and Michael N Johnstone. Selection of penetration testing methodologies: A comparison and evaluation. 2015.